

SUMMARY

ECONOMIC COMPETITION

by Prof. Mr J. Valkhoff

Before Worldwar II a law was passed on the declaration of binding or non-binding force of employer's agreements (1935). During and after that war the Cartel Degree of 1941 was in force with reference to enterprise regulations, with a later Act on the suspension of enterprise regulations in 1951. Just now the Draft Bill on Economic Competition (K.B. 24 Nov. 1953 No. 3295) is under consideration in Parliament, the principal juridical details of which are here given in outline against the back ground of the preceding statutory regulations.

In all three of them employer's agreements (1935) enterprise regulations (1941) and competition regulations (1953) are declared to be generally binding. „Enterprise regulations" cover a wider field than „employer's regulations". Agreements without binding force are also governed by this (Hoge Raad 2 June 1953).

„Competition-regulations" will on the other hand have a more limited scope. For the duty of entry (sanctioned by criminal law) and the duty of giving information, non-binding regulations to be specified later, may also be included as competition-regulations by Order in Council.

Whereas the prewar legal safeguards of legal security and objectivity of the binding declaration had disappeared in the Cartel Degree, the Draft Bill again has several of them: the description of the conditions and the procedure (by request only, the bearing of the Committee, on Economic Competition, of parties interested). The latter is a standing Committee, advising the Government (section 87 of the Constitution). She is independent and is not appointed from the „Sociaal-Economische Raad". The sanction on the binding declaration will again pertain to civil law.

Just like the Law on the Employer's Agreements and the Cartel Degree, the Draft Bill declares certain competition regulations to be of unbinding force by a similar procedure as the binding declaration. Partial or conditional non-binding declaration is also possible. A new addition is to be formed in the generic unbinding declaration by O.o.C. of competition regulations of a nature or tendency specified by that O.o.C. The author would in this case have liked to see a possibility of dispensation. The unbinding declaration will be sanctioned by criminal law (economic delict). This will also be the case with the regulation of the suspension of competition regulations (to a maximum of one year), which has been taken over by the Draft Bill.

The Draft Bill contains a separate regulation concerning the positions of economic power. To the Cabinet Ministers various exhaustively enumerated powers are given in cases where in their opinion there is a position of economic power which is against public interest. There is then both a civil and a criminal sanction of economic competition.

Both with reference to regulations and to positions of economic power, the Cabinet Ministers may require information and inspection of documents and papers.

The prohibition on complying with decisions in the field of Cartel policy of foreign states has not been limited in the Draft Bill to Dutch territory. It is improbable that in the further parliamentary consideration of the Draft Bill on Economic Competition a totally different system will be adopted, i.e. that of Cartel control by the judge instead of by the Administration. Some strengthening of the safeguards for legal security may however be expected.

The author mentions some possibilities of this.